

Virtual senses: Active cameras in improving online learning experience of St. Dominic College of Asia SASE students

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Abstract

Countless research have focused on online learning, and very few scholarly works examined online learning in terms of the broader student experience. This study aims to better understand the use of active cameras in improving the online learning experience of School of Arts, Sciences, and Education students in St. Dominic College of Asia using six factors: Participation and Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond, Efficient Communication, Motivation and Confidence, and Application. As defined in the study, active cameras are the use of video cameras throughout the online classes for both the teachers and the students. The researchers utilized a descriptive research design to define and interpret the current status of individuals, settings, or events (Mertler, 2014). This helped the researchers determine the cause-effect relationship of the variables: the student with an active camera and the camera itself. Researchers used an online survey via Google Forms to collect data. Using different statistical tools, the researchers found that most of the 131 respondents agreed that the use of active cameras improved their learning experience. Notably, it helps in enhancing their participation and productivity, presence, communication efficiency, and connection and bond with their teachers and classmates.

Keywords: Virtual senses, active cameras, online learning experience, webcam, online class.

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Introduction

In recent years, online learning has become increasingly popular across the higher education spectrum (Dunn, 2000). The expansive nature of the Internet and the accessibility of technology have generated a surge in demand for web-based teaching and learning (Chaney et al., 2010). Distance learning is a rapidly expanding environment that allows users the flexibility of operating outside of the constraints of time and place (Chaney et al., 2010). For decades, scholars have debated which mode of education is superior. Some argue that online is superior, and others say that online is less effective than traditional face-to-face courses. Still, others suggest that the hybrid mode (e.g., online blended with face-to-face lectures) is the most desired and productive content delivery method for students (Alsaaty et al., 2016). However, in March this year, President Rodrigo Duterte declared Metro Manila and the entire Luzon under enhanced community quarantine (ECQ) because of the coronavirus pandemic. As a result, the schools were asked to hold the remainder of their semester online; one of them is St. Dominic College of Asia.

There are indeed pros and cons in online learning; some must go to extremes to keep up. As a communication student, the first-hand struggle in online learning would be communication itself. There is a stigma created in a classroom format, making the thought of asking for clarification of a concept or responding to a discussion question seem quite unappealing. Since this would involve breaking the impenetrable silence, which accompanies all lectures students have attended so far (Reese, 2020). From the professor's perspective, it looks disheartening for them to discuss those black boxes—rather than actual faces. The capability to see your classmates and students more effectively imitates the typical in-person learning experience. People would feel less out of place asking a question or making a comment, and students would be able to read the classmates' facial expressions—the latter of which would be handy in a discussion-based course.

Synthesis of Related Literature

As COVID-19 continues to spread all across the globe, every event or gathering are now limited, including face-to-face classes. Hence, online classes are implemented in order to keep moving forward from the world's challenge to everyone. Despite the sudden change, classes were conducted online. Every activity and class discussions were made possible online. As students live in the 21st century, they are expected to adapt in the virtual classroom setup. Mahoney and Hall (2020) stated, "*Teaching and learning in the online environment are challenging. Students and instructors must employ technological tools and strategies to be successful.*" In addition, Farwell (2013) stated in his research, "*With the increasing use of smartphones, tablets, and other hand-held devices, it is important to keep pace with the students' preferred method of content delivery.*" With this in mind, every student must utilize the technology they have.

Utilizing every technology that the students are capable of accessing it is one of the things they should bring in facing online classes, especially if they are new and unfamiliar to the system. Learning how to incorporate virtual reality games, webcams, video conferencing, and brainstorming platforms such as Padlet, Bubbl.us, Zoom, Twitter, Instagram, interactive whiteboards, chat rooms, YouTube, and screen casting videos is encouraged (Mahoney & Hall, 2020). Devices such as smartphones and laptops have built-in webcams that can be used whenever something is needed to be seen virtually. Webcams or any cameras that can be easily accessed can be used in online classes as some web conferencing applications have a feature to use it. For one-on-one communication with instructors, free tools such as Skype and ooVoo can be adapted to allow the student and instructor to communicate using webcams, giving a sense of face-to-face personal interaction that is missing from email and chat (McCaslin & Brown, 2014).

Everyone in the world were forced to adapt in these trying times. Schools, especially in the Philippines where most schools are not yet integrated with online classes, were also forced to adapt due to COVID-19 pandemic in order for students to be safe as classes continues. Research of Khanum & Alam (2021) stated, "*Though to continue the regular race of education management and minimize the deficit the country has resorted to online classes, still it is a matter of doubt whether online classes are an equivalent substitute to the real physical classroom. It is because, keeping other problematic issues aside, to the learners, comprehending and grasping the contents of online lectures is much more challenging than that in the real classroom.*" Despite of the many challenges of online class, there is no doubt that students must do whatever is best and make the most out of everything they have in order to continue learning, whatever the process or system is.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to determine if the active camera improves the online learning experience of SASE students in St. Dominic College of Asia. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants according to:
 - a) Age
 - b) Gender
 - c) Course
 - d) Year
 - e) Section

2. What is the level of effectiveness of using camera during online classes in terms of:
 - a) Participation and Productivity
 - b) Presence
 - c) Connection and Bond
 - d) Efficient Communication
 - e) Motivation and Confidence
 - f) Application

3. Is there a significant difference in the levels of effectiveness of using active camera during online classes in terms of:
 - a) Participation and Productivity
 - b) Presence
 - c) Connection and Bond
 - d) Efficient Communication
 - e) Motivation and Confidence
 - f) Application

Methodology

This study aims to determine the experience of the respondents in having an active camera during the discussion in an online class. It will utilize the descriptive research design that will guide the researchers to identify the patterns between variables and define them. The objective of this design is to define and interpret the current status of individuals, settings, conditions, or events (Mertler, 2014). The respondents of the study are the 131 out of 207 students currently enrolled on the academic year 2020-2021 under the School of Arts, Sciences, and Education (SASE) department at St. Dominic College of Asia. The students in question were students enrolled in Bachelor of Arts in Communication, Bachelor of Science in Psychology, and Bachelor of Science in Education.

Convenience sampling was utilized in this research. This method belongs to non-probability sampling techniques; respondents who are fit for the research are chosen conveniently as researchers' source of data. According to Kempf-Leonard (2005), there is no pattern whatsoever in acquiring these respondents. He also stated that it can be helpful in obtaining a range of attitudes

and opinions and in identifying tentative hypotheses that can be evaluated more rigorously in further research. The researchers used questionnaires that contained the questions to answer about this topic to obtain the required information from each student and professors. In addition, the researchers made the questionnaire itself that contains the age, course, year, and section of the demographic to identify the demographic of the samples. The questionnaire also contains questions regarding the students' participation and productivity, presence, connection and bond, efficient communication, motivation and confidence, and application when using active cameras in a synchronous class. The questions and categories were based on the related literatures and studies to further solidify and support the questionnaire. The research was conducted amidst the pandemic. Therefore, the questionnaires were sent in a Google Forms online to respondents.

Cross-tabulation method is the most appropriate method since it uses a basic tabular form to draw inferences between different data-sets in the research study. It contains data that is mutually exclusive or has some connection with each other.

The researchers computed for One-way Repeated Measures ANOVA (dependent- or within-samples ANOVA) using SPSS version 26 (IBM, 2019) to analyze if there are significant differences in the level of agreement in terms of effectiveness of using camera during online classes in six (6) different categories (i.e., Participation and Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond, Efficient Communication, Motivation and Confidence, and Application) and the Overall Effectiveness. To further understand the significant differences between the categories or areas of effectiveness, a Pairwise Comparisons test was used to see the mean differences between each of those areas.

Table 1. Five-point Likert scale

Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
3.41 – 4.20	Agree
2.61 – 3.40	Undecided
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree

Results

The participants consisted of students from the three (3) programs of the School of Arts, Sciences, and Education of St. Dominic College of Asia, having mostly students from the BS Psychology program (103 out of 131 participants, or 78.6%). The respondents' ages range from 18-43, with those in the age group of 20-24 being the majority of the participants (93 or 72%). Most of these students are females (97 or 74%), having only 28 males (or ~21%).

Table 2. Frequency table of the respondents' age profile

Age	Frequency	Percentage
19 years old and below	29	22.1
20-24 years old	93	71.0
25-29 years old	3	2.3
30-34 years old	3	2.3
35 years old and above	3	2.3
Total (N)	131	100

Table 2 shows the frequency distribution of the age of each respondent and its percentage. A total of 131 respondents, mostly of students under 20-24 years old with a frequency of 93 and a percentage of 71%. It was followed by students 19 years old and below with a frequency of 29 and a percentage of 22.1%. Lastly, students under 25-29 years old, 30-34 years old, and 35 years old and above, all shared a frequency of three (3) with a percentage of 2.3%.

Table 3. Frequency table of the respondents' gender profile

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	97	74.0
Male	28	21.4
Bisexual	1	0.8
Gender Fluid	1	0.8
Prefer not to say	4	3.1
Total (N)	131	100

Table 3 shows the frequency distribution of the gender of the respondents. A total of 131 respondents with a majority of female students with a frequency of 97 and 74%, followed by male students (28 or 21.4%). At the same time, some students prefer not to say their gender with four (4) or 3.1%, and a bisexual and a gender-fluid student who share the same frequency of one (1) and a percentage of 0.8%.

Table 4. Frequency table of the respondents' course, year, and section profile

Course	Year and Section	Frequency	Percentage
BA Communication	1A	3	2.3
	2A	4	3.1
	3A	1	0.8
	4A	6	4.6
	Total	14	10.7
BS Education	2A	3	2.3
	3A	5	3.8
	4A	6	4.6
	Total	14	10.7
BS Psychology	1A	18	13.7
	1B	1	0.8
	2A	42	32.1
	2B	3	2.3
	3A	30	22.9
	4A	9	6.9
	Total	103	78.6
Total (N)		131	100

Table 4 shows the frequency distribution of the students' course, year, and section, with a total of 131 respondents which comprises of students enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Psychology (103 or 78.6%), Bachelor of Science in Education (14 or 10.7%), and Bachelor of Arts in Communication (14 or 10.7%). In addition, respondents in BA Communication comprises of students under 1A (3 or 2.3%), 2A (4 or 3.1%), 3A (1 or 0.8%), and 4A (6 or 4.6%). Respondents under BS Education consist of students under 2A (3 or 2.3%), 3A (5 or 3.8%), and 4A (6 or 4.6%). Lastly, BS Psychology consists of respondents under their respective year and section which comprises of 1A (18 or 13.7%), 1B (1 or 0.8%), 2A (42 or 32.1%), 2B (3 or 2.3%), 3A (30 or 22.9%), and 4A (9 or 6.9%).

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of the level of agreement of the effectiveness of using camera during online classes (N=131)

Variables	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Participation and Productivity	3.98	.73	Agree
Presence	3.97	.65	Agree
Connection and Bond	3.52	.78	Agree
Efficient Communication	3.61	.81	Agree
Motivation and Confidence	3.35	.94	Undecided
Application	3.36	.73	Undecided
Overall Effectiveness	3.63	.61	Agree

The researchers computed for One-way Repeated Measures ANOVA (dependent- or within-samples ANOVA) using SPSS version 26 (IBM, 2019) to analyze if there are significant differences in the level of agreement in terms of the effectiveness of using camera during online classes in six (6) different categories (i.e., Participation and Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond, Efficient Communication, Motivation and Confidence, and Application) and the Overall Effectiveness.

Table 5 shows the level of agreement of the effectiveness of using camera during online classes from the gathered data of 131 students. In the result, it shows that students "Agree" in the categories of Participation and Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond, and Efficient Communication. This means that students acknowledge the effectiveness of using cameras during online classes. It indicates that an active camera is significant to the students in terms of these categories. However, students doubt the effectiveness of active cameras during online classes in the categories of Motivation and Confidence and Application. It explains that the presence of a camera during class is not exhibiting significance in terms of students' Motivation and Confidence and the application itself.

Descriptive statistics were computed to examine the level of agreement of the participants in terms of the effectiveness of using camera during online classes in six (6) various categories (i.e., Participation and Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond, Efficient Communication, Motivation and Confidence, and Application) and the Overall Effectiveness. The results reveal that the participants agree that using camera as part of the synchronous online classes is effective in the improvement of their: Participation and Productivity (M=3.98, SD=.73), Presence (M=3.97, SD=.65), Connection and Bond (M=3.52, SD=.78), and Efficient Communication (M=3.61, SD=.81).

However, the results also show that the students are undecided if camera use is also effective in their Motivation and Confidence ($M=3.35$, $SD=.94$) and Application ($M=3.36$, $SD=.73$). Despite this varying agreement in the effectiveness, the findings suggest that the students still agree about its positive Overall Effectiveness ($M=3.63$, $SD=.61$).

Table 6. One-way within-subjects ANOVA statistics of the effectiveness of using camera during online classes (N=131)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Effectiveness	53.127	4.419	12.024	37.966	.000	.226
Error (Effectiveness)	181.914	574.411	.317			

The researchers computed for One-way Repeated Measures ANOVA (dependent- or within-samples ANOVA) using SPSS version 26 (IBM, 2019) to analyze if there are significant differences in the level of agreement in terms of the effectiveness of using camera during online classes in six (6) different categories (i.e., Participation and Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond, Efficient Communication, Motivation and Confidence, and Application) and the Overall Effectiveness. The results reveal that there are significant differences among all the categories and the overall effectiveness of camera use [$F(4.42, 574.41) = 37.97$, $p=.000$].

Table 7. Pairwise comparisons of the mean differences in the different areas of effectiveness of using camera during online classes (N=131)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	-						
2	.009	-					
3	.461*	.452*	-				
4	.373*	.363*	-.089	-			
5	.632*	.623*	.171*	.260*	-		
6	.623*	.614*	.162*	.250*	-.009	-	
7	.349*	.340*	-.112*	-.023	-.283*	-.274*	-

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

(1 – Participation and Productivity; 2 – Presence; 3 – Connection and Bond; 4 – Efficient Communication; 5 – Motivation and Confidence; 6 – Application; 7 – Overall Effectiveness)

To further understand the significant differences between the categories or areas of effectiveness, Table 7 shows a Pairwise Comparisons test that was used to see the mean differences between each of those areas. The findings suggest that almost all of them show differences except between Participation and Productivity to Presence ($MD=.009$, $p=.876$); Connection and Bond to Efficient Communication ($MD=-.089$, $p=.136$); Motivation and Confidence to Application ($MD=-.009$, $p=.886$); and Overall Effectiveness to Efficient Communication ($MD=-.023$, $p=.563$).

The survey respondents were higher grade level students and newly working individuals (20-24 years old) who prefer further analysis and clarification of topics discussed using active cameras. Likewise, it showed that respondents of those ages visually learn effectively as they were exposed to the speaker and other participants.

As to consider the gender of the respondents, it was manifested in the frequency that females mostly answered the survey, followed by male students. Moreover, respondents of higher age manifested reluctance in answering questionnaires as only three (3) from each age bracket of

25-29, 30-34, and 40-43 years old shared their point of view on the use of active cameras during the discussion in an online class.

Participation and Productivity deal with the performance of students during an online class. It explains how students involved themselves in the class and understood the lesson. According to Bettinger et al. (2017), we must design online learning environments to develop significant interactions. The respondents agreed that an active camera in the course of the online class contributed to the effective improvement of their Participation and productivity. The total mean got 3.98 with the interpretation of agree. The utilization of cameras helped students to improve their academic performance. The students' active participation can be a key factor in determining the success of online classes (Song et al., 2019).

The Presence category covers the appearance of the students during the class. According to Oztok and Brett's (2011) review of the research as cited by Preisman (2014), the idea of presence is historically viewed through the eyes of the learners with a specific focus on strategies to create a presence in the online setting. Considering the situation of distance learning where students could join the class in whatever place they preferred to be, the usage of cameras observed the student's improvement. With a total mean of 3.98 and an agreement interpretation, the respondents considered the active camera significant to improving their presence during an online class.

The third category, Connection and Bond, had the weighted mean of 3.98 and .73 SD, resulting in the verbal interpretation of "Agree." The fourth category, Efficient Communication, displayed the weighted mean of 3.61 and .94 SD, providing the verbal interpretation of "Agree". These two categories are inclined with Moore's model, which provides motivation, feedback, and dialogue between the teacher and student identified as Learner-instructor interaction. This is also supported by the earlier work of Collis (1996), who claimed that interaction and a sense of contribution could be enhanced through the use of the synchronous system and synchronous tools.

On the other hand, the results showed that students were undecided if using an active camera is effective in the Motivation, Confidence, and Application categories. This showed that students were neutral to the notion that using the camera might boost their confidence and motivate them to learn inside a virtual classroom, and they were simply uncertain of using the feature itself. Islam stated that although research shows that web conferencing can be an effective tool for various professional course offerings, there is little evidence of its usefulness serving as a primary course delivery format (Knapczyk et al., 2005).

Moreover, research by Gherheş et al. (2021), which focused on finding and understanding the reason behind the student's behavior on their take regarding usage of webcams, showed that more than half of the students participating in the study reported that they do not agree to keep their webcams on during online classes, the main reasons being anxiety/fear of being exposed/shame/shyness, desire to ensure the privacy of the home/personal space, and chances that other people might walk into the background.

However, despite the two categories resulted as "undecided" for the "Motivation and Confidence" and "Application" categories, the overall effectiveness said otherwise, and students still thought that using cameras might improve their online learning experience inside a virtual classroom.

Table 6 analyzed if there are significant differences in the level of agreement regarding the effectiveness of using camera during online classes in six distinct categories. These results suggested that the use of camera during online synchronous classes might have varying effects on different areas of experience among college students.

With the help of a Pairwise Comparisons test, Table 7 revealed that almost all showed differences except between: Participation and Productivity to Presence; Connection and Bond to Efficient Communication; Motivation and Confidence to Application; and Overall Effectiveness to Efficient Communication. The results suggested that using a camera during online classes might influence those areas without significant differences almost to the same extent or degree. With this, the participation and presence might be improved at around the same level. This, likewise, applies to the connection and communication, the motivation and application, and the overall effectiveness and communications.

Discussion

Analyzing the demographic of our respondents, 78.6% or 103 of them were commonly Psychology students while both Communication and Education students were at 10.7% or 14 of them each has answered the survey. The respondents were mostly in the age range of 20-24 years old at 71% or 93 of them while 22.1% or 29 of them were aged 18-19 years and only 2.3 or 3 of them each were aged 25-29, 30-34 and 40-43 years. Moreover, the gender of respondents was mostly female at 97 or 74%, while males were 28 or 22.1%, and those who did not mention were at 4 or 3.1% and both of those who were Bisexual, and Gender Fluid were at one (1) or 0.8%.

The result of this research provided evidence to support that the presence of an active camera during an online class improved the online learning of students at St. Dominic College of Asia. A total of 131 respondents from the three programs of the School of Arts, Sciences, and Education with ages range from 18-43. Participants are mostly females, and most respondents are from the BS Psychology program.

The effectiveness of each category, namely, Participation & Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond, and Efficient Communication had a decent and high statistics of based on the results and it was agreed by the respondents when it comes to the effectiveness. However, Motivation and Confidence and Application resulted in “undecided.”

An active camera breaks the gap of distance learning of student to students' relationship and professor to students' connection. It creates a light environment and avoids the sense of isolation. The interaction and appearance enhanced the academic performance and quality of online learning. The use of the active camera plays a significant role in terms of students' Participation and Productivity, Presence, Connection and Bond and Efficient Communication. The presence of this exhibits a great level of effectiveness and impact on the students. However, cameras manifest a poor level of effectiveness in terms of Motivation and Confidence and Application as students were hesitant to consider the contribution of the active cameras during an online class on their confidence and motivation to learn in a virtual setting. It explained that the determination to improve their academic performance had nothing to do with the presence of the camera. Furthermore, the application itself like Zoom, Google Meet, and other video conference platforms, and how students approach the usage of active cameras was also not considered as a

key factor. With this information, it states the significant difference in the levels of effectiveness of using cameras during discussion towards the six categories. The presence of a camera gives an improvement in students' academic performance and interaction with each other but not in their character as a person and student.

Recapitulating, this research sought to make two contributions: (1) seek aid in better understanding of active cameras in improving the online learning experience of students, (2) serve as a contribution to develop knowledge in this particular field of study for future researchers. Based on the findings and conclusions, the researchers recommend the implementation of using active cameras during online synchronous classes in educational institutions while filling the gap in improving the students' motivation and confidence and the application of using active cameras. This research is designed to analyze statistical data in order to emerge a conclusion. Future researchers may resort to pursuing qualitative research with a similar or related research topic to further analyze and understand the issue and behavior of students.

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